

**ENHANCING NEAR INFRARED FACE
RECOGNITION BY REFOCUSING
ATTENTION ON CRITICAL FACIAL
FEATURES**

PHASE II REPORT

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BONAFIDE CERTIFICATE

Certified that this project report titled “**ENHANCING NEAR INFRARED FACE RECOGNITION BY REFOCUSING ATTENTION ON CRITICAL FACIAL FEATURES** ” is the *bonafide* work of ”**HEMASREE SENTHIL(3122215001034)**” who carried out the project work under my supervision.

Certified further that to the best of my knowledge the work reported herein does not form part of any other thesis or dissertation on the basis of which a degree or award was conferred on an earlier occasion on this or any other candidate.

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ABSTRACT

Face recognition using Near-Infrared (NIR) images offers a powerful alternative to traditional visible spectrum imaging, particularly in low-light and challenging lighting conditions where visible light struggles to capture clear facial features. NIR imaging enables reliable feature capture in such environments, making it highly suitable for applications in security and surveillance. This project enhances model accuracy for NIR images by leveraging advanced deep learning architectures specifically optimized for NIR challenges, such as low contrast and lighting variability. Key methods include detailed preprocessing to improve image clarity, data augmentation to increase dataset quality to boost feature extraction and identity preservation. Various models, including ResNet, Vision Transformer and hybrid architecture, are rigorously evaluated on CASIA NIR-VIS 2.0 and LAMPHQ datasets to determine the most effective approach, aiming to improve recognition accuracy and robustness in NIR imaging and provide a more adaptable, reliable solution for real-world applications.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Near-Infrared (NIR) imaging offers significant advantages for face recognition, particularly under challenging lighting conditions, where traditional visible-spectrum cameras may fail. Unlike visible-light imaging as seen in Figure 1.1, which is highly sensitive to ambient light variations and often results in inconsistent facial feature capture, NIR-based systems depicted in the Figure 1.2 excel at capturing clear and consistent facial details. This reliability extends across diverse lighting settings, from brightly lit areas to shadows or fluctuating light environments. The unique ability of NIR imaging to function effectively in low light conditions makes it particularly suitable for scenarios such as nighttime surveillance or low illuminated indoor spaces, where visible-light cameras often struggle to capture sufficient detail for accurate recognition.

FIGURE 1.1: Visible spectrum images in varying light

FIGURE 1.2: NIR spectrum images in varying light

This advantage makes NIR particularly valuable for critical applications such as security, surveillance, and access control systems, where consistent and accurate face recognition is essential regardless of lighting conditions. By capturing sharp and detailed features in near-darkness, NIR-based face recognition systems support continuous monitoring without the need for additional artificial lighting, which not only saves energy but also preserves natural settings in sensitive

environments. Furthermore, the non-intrusive nature of NIR imaging aligns well with privacy-conscious applications, as it allows for clear imaging without using visible light that could draw attention or cause discomfort.

Additionally, NIR technology is beneficial for mobile or portable devices that require robust facial recognition without relying on ideal lighting. This adaptability makes NIR face recognition suitable for broader deployments across urban, rural, and industrial settings where lighting variability is common. In essence, the stability and adaptability of NIR imaging offer a powerful solution for real-time, accurate face recognition in scenarios where visible light technology may otherwise be limited, making it an indispensable tool in modern biometric systems.

1.1 MOTIVATION

The motivation behind this project arises from the need to improve facial recognition accuracy in challenging lighting environments, where traditional visible spectrum imaging often falls short. Visible light cameras, while effective in controlled settings, are susceptible to variations in lighting, shadows, and low-light conditions, making them less reliable in diverse real-world applications. This limitation is particularly problematic for fields like security, surveillance, and access control, where consistent and accurate face recognition is essential.

Near-Infrared (NIR) imaging provides a promising alternative by capturing facial features clearly in variable and low-light environments, enabling dependable recognition where visible light systems struggle. Operating outside the visible

spectrum, NIR imaging can penetrate darkness and maintain consistent feature capture even under fluctuating or minimal ambient light. This capability makes NIR especially advantageous for applications like nighttime surveillance, low-light indoor monitoring, and security-sensitive areas that cannot rely on additional lighting for effective monitoring.

Furthermore, NIR-based recognition aligns with the demand for non-intrusive, privacy-conscious biometric technologies. Since NIR wavelengths are invisible to the human eye, they enable discreet monitoring without visible illumination, making it ideal for public security and personal device authentication, where privacy and user comfort are a priority. By focusing on NIR images, this project bridges the gap in facial recognition accuracy found in visible spectrum-based models, enhancing performance and broadening the range of practical applications. These advancements contribute to the development of robust, adaptable, and privacy-respecting facial recognition systems capable of operating seamlessly across varied lighting conditions.

1.2 BACKGROUND

This project advances facial recognition technology by leveraging Near-Infrared (NIR) imaging to address limitations in traditional visible spectrum-based models, which typically perform well only under controlled, well-lit conditions. In low-light or variable lighting environments, visible light-based models often fail to capture essential facial details, leading to reduced recognition accuracy. NIR imaging, however, can capture clearer facial features even under challenging lighting conditions, making it ideal for applications such as nighttime security

monitoring, indoor surveillance, and secure access control where reliable performance across diverse lighting conditions is essential.

To fully utilize the advantages of NIR imaging, this project applies advanced deep learning architectures, such as ResNet, which are highly effective in extracting complex facial features. The model is further optimized with a modified loss function tailored to NIR data, maximizing feature separability and enhancing accuracy. Additionally, a contrast-based preprocessing technique is implemented, where Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE)[10] is applied for high-contrast enhancement, while Gaussian blur or gamma correction is used for low-contrast normalization. This multi-level contrast adjustment ensures that facial features are well-preserved and distinguishable under varying lighting conditions. By integrating these deep learning techniques with contrast-enhanced NIR imaging, this project aims to develop a robust and adaptable facial recognition system capable of performing reliably in challenging environments, expanding its potential applications in security and surveillance.

1.3 PROBLEM DEFINITION

The problem this project addresses the limited reliability of face recognition models trained on visible spectrum images, which struggle under lighting variations or low light. While effective in controlled, well-lit environments, their accuracy drops significantly in real-world settings with inconsistent lighting, posing challenges for security, surveillance, and authentication applications. To overcome this, the project adapts face recognition models to utilize Near-Infrared (NIR) images, which capture clear facial details even in near-darkness, shadows,

and low-light settings. NIR imaging ensures reliable recognition without additional light sources, making it ideal for nighttime surveillance, indoor security, and mobile authentication. By incorporating advanced deep learning techniques, including modified architectures this project enhances accuracy and robustness, creating a versatile system capable of performing reliably across diverse conditions.

1.4 ORGANIZATION OF REPORT

The report is organized as follows. Chapter 2 presents a comprehensive literature survey on Near-Infrared (NIR) face recognition and highlights the existing research gaps. Chapter 3 outlines the proposed methodology, including dataset collection, three-channel preprocessing techniques such as CLAHE and gamma correction, and the architecture of the face recognition models employed (ResNet, EfficientNet, and Vision Transformer). Chapter 4 details the experimental results and performance analysis, including accuracy metrics, interpretability scores, and heatmap visualizations. Chapter 5 describes the experimental setup, including hardware and software configurations used for model training and evaluation. Chapter 6 explores the social impact and sustainability of using NIR-based face recognition technology. Finally, Chapter 7 concludes the report with key findings and outlines potential directions for future research.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

This literature survey examines recent advancements in Near-Infrared (NIR) face recognition, emphasizing the role of optimized models and advanced attention mechanisms in achieving high accuracy. As NIR face recognition becomes increasingly important in various security and identification applications, researchers have focused on developing techniques that can effectively handle the unique challenges posed by NIR images. Key innovations include the integration of attention mechanisms like self-attention and cross-attention, which allow models to selectively concentrate on critical facial features. By leveraging these cutting-edge techniques, recent approaches have significantly enhanced the robustness and reliability of NIR face recognition systems, making them more applicable in real-world scenarios where precision and accuracy are paramount.

2.1 PAPERS RELATED TO THE PROBLEM IDENTIFIED

In [10], Purnawarman Musa et al. explored the application of Contrast-Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) in facial recognition, emphasizing its role in enhancing image contrast while mitigating the over-amplification of noise. Their study focused on improving live-stream facial recognition using the Local Binary Pattern Histogram (LBPH) method, where varying lighting conditions posed a challenge to accurate recognition. By integrating CLAHE as a

preprocessing step, the system effectively adapted to intensity variations, ensuring better feature extraction and improved recognition accuracy. Their findings highlight CLAHE significance in biometric authentication, demonstrating its effectiveness in addressing common issues such as uneven illumination and low-contrast images, making it a valuable technique for robust facial recognition systems.

In [1], Chambino reviewed multispectral facial recognition techniques, emphasizing the integration of different spectral modalities, including visible (VIS), near-infrared (NIR), and thermal images. The paper highlights the challenges associated with cross-spectrum matching, such as significant modality variations and lack of standardization across datasets. The authors analyzed advancements in feature extraction, image synthesis, and fusion strategies that enhance cross-spectrum recognition performance. Key methodologies, including deep learning-based approaches and hybrid techniques, are discussed for their ability to address spectral variability and improve recognition accuracy. This review provides valuable insights into the state-of-the-art in multispectral facial recognition and outlines potential directions for future research.

In [11], Sergey Zagoruyko and Nikos Komodakis explored the role of attention in improving convolutional neural networks (CNNs) by leveraging attention transfer from a teacher network to a student network. Their approach defines attention as spatial maps that highlight the most influential regions in an image during classification, capturing low-level, mid-level, and high-level feature representations. Inspired by this, our implementation integrates attention mechanisms within our CNN model to enhance feature extraction and decision-making. By utilizing activation-based and gradient-based attention

maps, we enable the model to focus on the most relevant facial features, improving robustness in challenging conditions such as varying contrast and illumination. This incorporation of attention mechanisms ensures that our model prioritizes discriminative features, leading to enhanced performance in NIR-based facial recognition.

In [9], Maysanjaya et al. evaluated various contrast enhancement methods for improving the visibility of finger vein patterns in NIR images, a crucial aspect of biometric authentication. Despite the advantages of NIR imaging in capturing sub-surface vein structures, factors such as skin thickness and ambient lighting can obscure the clarity of vein patterns. To address this, the study compared the performance of several contrast enhancement techniques, including Histogram Equalization (HE), Adaptive Histogram Equalization (AHE), and Contrast-Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE), alongside the proposed Bi-Histogram Equalization with Plateau Limit and Dual Gamma Correction (BPDFHE) method. Their findings demonstrated that BPDFHE outperformed other techniques in metrics such as Absolute Mean Brightness Error (AMBE), Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), Structural Similarity Index (SSIM), and Feature Similarity Index (FSIM), while also achieving lower computation time. This research highlights the significance of contrast enhancement in optimizing NIR-based biometric systems, reinforcing the necessity of effective preprocessing techniques for reliable vein-based authentication.

In [5], Zhang et al. explored multimodal image fusion using the CrossFuse method, which introduces a cross-attention mechanism (CAM) within a two-stage training strategy. By focusing on complementary inter-modality features and

reducing redundancy, the approach outperforms traditional transformer-based methods. This method is particularly effective in maintaining salient features and generating accurate fused images, making it highly applicable in tasks like surveillance and high-quality image synthesis.

In [6], the authors described the Low-Rank Transformer (LRT) model, designed to process high-resolution hyperspectral imaging data efficiently. The paper addresses the computational and memory challenges posed by high-dimensional hyperspectral datasets, proposing a transformer-based architecture with low-rank decomposition to reduce complexity while preserving critical spectral and spatial information. By capturing long-range dependencies and fine-grained details across spectral bands, the LRT demonstrates superior performance in tasks like image reconstruction and classification. Experimental results on benchmark hyperspectral datasets show that LRT achieves state-of-the-art accuracy while maintaining computational efficiency, making it a promising solution for applications in remote sensing, medical imaging, and environmental monitoring.

In [7], the authors addressed the challenge of heterogeneous face recognition between near-infrared (NIR) and visible light (VIS) modalities by introducing a method to transfer deep feature representations for improved cross-spectrum matching. The study leverages a shared feature space to bridge the gap between NIR and VIS images. By employing a deep convolutional neural network (CNN) trained with a joint loss function combining identity and modality-specific constraints, the method enhances feature alignment across modalities. Experimental evaluations on benchmark datasets demonstrate significant improvements in recognition accuracy, establishing the effectiveness of the proposed approach for heterogeneous face recognition tasks.

In [9], Sekiguchi and Yamamoto discussed a deep learning framework for colorizing NIR images. By combining pixel-wise loss with perceptual loss derived from a pretrained VGG19 network, the authors created a method that ensures basic color accuracy while capturing high-level semantic features. This approach effectively addresses challenges like noise sensitivity and lack of semantic understanding, producing visually coherent colorizations. The framework generalizes well to unseen images, enhancing their usability for automated processing and visual interpretation in fields such as surveillance and ecological studies.

In [8], Tang et al. highlighted the MATR model for multimodal medical image fusion, focusing on its relevance in integrating NIR images with modalities like SPECT and MRI. The model employs a dual loss function combining structural-level and region mutual information (RMI) losses, preserving critical information while capturing global context through an adaptive Transformer module. This methodology exploits complementary features across modalities, producing high-quality fused images that enhance diagnostic capabilities in medical applications.

In [15], Khan et al. provided a comprehensive survey on Vision Transformers (ViTs) and their hybrid CNN-Transformer variants, highlighting their growing significance in computer vision. Vision Transformers leverage self-attention mechanisms to capture global relationships in images, offering high learning capacity. However, they often struggle with local feature extraction, which CNNs excel at. To overcome this limitation, hybrid architectures integrating convolutional operations with self-attention have emerged, combining the strengths of both approaches. These CNN-Transformer models have demonstrated superior performance across various vision tasks by effectively

modeling both local and global representations. The survey presents a taxonomy of these hybrid architectures, discussing key components such as attention mechanisms, positional embeddings, and multi-scale processing. By exploring the advancements in hybrid vision transformers, this study highlights their potential to enhance feature extraction and generalization, paving the way for more efficient and robust deep learning models in computer vision applications.

2.2 GAPS IDENTIFIED

The identified research gaps highlight limitations in existing NIR face recognition methods, such as inadequate feature preservation and limited adaptability across lighting conditions.

2.2.1 Limited Data Diversity in NIR Datasets

Many existing methods rely on limited or constrained NIR datasets, which often lack sufficient variation in terms of lighting, pose, and subject diversity. This limitation hinders the generalizability of face recognition models across diverse environments and conditions, especially in real-world applications where lighting and facial expressions vary widely. The lack of diverse data also limits the model adaptability to new subjects and unseen conditions. Addressing this gap requires the development of more comprehensive datasets or effective data augmentation techniques to improve the robustness and versatility of NIR models.

2.2.2 Need for More Robust Preprocessing Techniques in NIR Images

Despite the advancements in image preprocessing techniques, many traditional methods such as Histogram Equalization (HE), Adaptive Histogram Equalization (AHE), and Contrast-Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) have not been widely explored for NIR-based face recognition. Most deep learning models are designed and optimized for visible spectrum images, overlooking the unique characteristics of NIR data, such as lower contrast and reduced texture detail. This gap in research has led to suboptimal feature extraction, limiting the model ability to differentiate between fine facial details in NIR images. To address this, our approach integrates contrast enhancement techniques tailored for NIR images, ensuring better feature preservation and improving overall model performance. By employing preprocessing methods such as CLAHE for high-contrast enhancement and Gaussian blur or gamma correction for low-contrast normalization, we aim to optimize the input representation before feeding it into the deep learning model, ultimately enhancing recognition accuracy in challenging conditions.

2.2.3 Challenges in Recognizing Critical Features in NIR Face Recognition

A major challenge in NIR-based face recognition is the difficulty in capturing critical facial features due to the inherent differences between RGB and NIR imaging. Most face recognition models are trained on visible spectrum images,

where color information and high-frequency textures aid in feature discrimination. However, NIR images lack color channels and often exhibit reduced texture details, making it harder for models to extract meaningful representations. This discrepancy is evident in Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping (Grad-CAM) visualizations, which show that models trained on RGB images tend to focus on color-dependent features rather than structural details, leading to suboptimal performance when applied to NIR data. Addressing this challenge requires refining feature extraction methods to ensure that models focus on shape, contrast, and edge-based information rather than relying on color-based cues. By integrating specialized preprocessing techniques and adjusting model architectures to prioritize structural features, we aim to improve the robustness of NIR-based face recognition under varied conditions.

2.2.4 Limited Robustness of NIR Models for Generalized Applications

Current NIR-based models are often optimized for specific tasks or controlled settings but may struggle in varied real-world scenarios, such as dynamic lighting or outdoor environments. This limitation restricts their usability in broader applications that demand high reliability across diverse conditions, especially in critical areas like surveillance and security. A gap remains in developing NIR models with enhanced adaptability, emphasizing advanced architectures, improved training techniques, and adaptive components to boost robustness and flexibility in real-world applications.

2.3 RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

The research objectives aim to address key gaps identified in the current body of work on NIR-based face recognition. These objectives focus on enhancing feature extraction, improving model robustness, and developing tailored loss functions for optimized NIR-based recognition, ultimately working towards a more adaptable and reliable face recognition system under varied conditions.

2.3.1 Enhance Face Recognition Accuracy in NIR Images

One primary objective of this project is to improve the accuracy of face recognition models by adapting deep learning architectures, such as Residual Networks (ResNet), specifically for NIR images. NIR images present unique challenges that differ significantly from visible spectrum images, primarily due to lower contrast, monochromatic data, and lighting variability across different environments. Standard deep learning architectures trained on visible light images may not perform optimally with NIR data, which lacks the color and texture variations typically present in RGB images. By focusing on these unique challenges, the project aims to enable reliable and accurate face recognition performance in a variety of lighting conditions, from low-light environments to those with rapidly changing ambient lighting. This objective is crucial for enhancing the applicability of NIR-based face recognition in real-world applications, such as nighttime surveillance and low-light security settings.

2.3.2 Limitations of RGB-Trained Models in NIR Face Recognition

Many existing face recognition models are trained on large-scale RGB datasets, leading to suboptimal performance when applied to NIR images. One major challenge is that these models rely on color-based features, which are absent in NIR images, causing them to misinterpret important facial structures. This project examines how models trained on RGB datasets fail to focus on relevant facial features in NIR images using Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping (Grad-CAM) visualizations. By identifying these limitations, this research aims to develop strategies to refine deep learning architectures for better NIR adaptability, ensuring models extract meaningful structural information rather than depending on color-based distinctions.

2.3.3 Impact of Contrast Enhancement on Deep Learning Models

This project investigates how contrast-enhanced NIR images influence the performance of deep learning architectures used for face recognition. By integrating contrast enhancement techniques into the preprocessing pipeline, this study aims to improve feature extraction, thereby increasing recognition accuracy. The impact of these enhancements will be evaluated using multiple CNN architectures to determine the extent to which preprocessing contributes to improved model performance.

CHAPTER 3

PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

This study focuses on improving feature extraction, by constructing a 3-channel image representation by applying CLAHE for high-contrast enhancement, gamma correction for low-contrast normalization, and retaining the raw NIR image as an additional channel. This multi-channel approach ensures that deep learning models receive enriched feature maps, improving facial structure visibility for recognition tasks. The Figure 3.1 describes the methodology in detail.

To assess the impact of this preprocessing, we train deep learning models, including ResNet, EfficientNet, and Vision Transformer (ViT). ResNet serves as the baseline due to its strong performance in image recognition tasks. EfficientNet is included for its parameter efficiency and adaptability, while ViT allows us to explore the role of attention-based architectures in NIR face recognition. The models are trained on both raw NIR images and contrast-enhanced 3-channel images to compare the impact of preprocessing. Transfer learning is employed to accelerate convergence, and data augmentation techniques are applied to improve robustness against variations in pose, illumination, and occlusions.

To better understand how these models process NIR face images, we employ Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping (Grad-CAM). Grad-CAM generates heatmaps that highlight the most influential facial regions for each model decision-making process. Since most deep learning architectures are trained on visible spectrum (RGB) images, they may struggle to focus on

meaningful features in NIR images. By analyzing Grad-CAM outputs across ResNet, EfficientNet, and ViT, we investigate whether contrast-enhanced preprocessing improves feature localization. These insights help determine if preprocessing techniques guide models toward more relevant facial regions.

Model performance is evaluated using accuracy-based and explainability-driven metrics. Standard recognition metrics such as Top-1 and Top-5 accuracy measure classification effectiveness. Additionally, Deletion Metric and Insertion Metric assess the importance of extracted features in Grad-CAM visualizations. The Deletion Metric measures how quickly model confidence drops when removing key features, while the Insertion Metric quantifies confidence improvements when key features are added. We also calculate the Intersection over Union (IoU) Score, which evaluates how well Grad-CAM heatmaps align with facial regions. These metrics provide deeper insights into how preprocessing affects both recognition accuracy and model interpretability.

To ensure generalization, trained models are tested across CASIA NIR-VIS 2.0 and LAMP-HQ. Many NIR-based face recognition models perform well on controlled datasets but struggle in real-world scenarios due to lighting variations, facial occlusions, and pose changes. Cross-dataset validation helps assess whether contrast-enhanced preprocessing improves robustness under different conditions. Additionally, comparing CNN-based models (ResNet, EfficientNet) with Transformer-based models (ViT) helps identify which architecture generalizes best to NIR images.

Finally, we conduct a comparative analysis to summarize key findings. We evaluate whether contrast-enhanced 3-channel preprocessing improves feature extraction and compare model behavior across different architectures. Grad-CAM

visualizations, deletion and insertion metrics, and IoU scores help explain how models process NIR images differently. The study concludes by identifying the most effective techniques for enhancing NIR face recognition and outlines potential future work, such as adaptive contrast enhancement or further optimization of hybrid CNN-Transformer architectures.

Moreover, the insights gained from the Grad-CAM visualizations allow for a deeper understanding of how different models focus on facial regions in NIR images. By analyzing activation maps, we assess whether CNN-based models like ResNet and EfficientNet rely on local edge-based features, while ViT captures more global dependencies. This comparison helps determine the most suitable architecture for NIR face recognition, particularly in challenging conditions such as low-light environments and occlusions. Furthermore, the impact of contrast-enhanced preprocessing on feature localization provides valuable evidence on how multi-channel representations contribute to improving model attention toward discriminative facial features.

In addition to evaluating performance across architectures, the study also highlights the importance of designing NIR-specific preprocessing pipelines tailored to deep learning models. While traditional models have been optimized for visible spectrum images, our findings suggest that leveraging contrast enhancement techniques, such as CLAHE and gamma correction, can significantly bridge the gap between RGB-trained models and NIR face recognition.

FIGURE 3.1: Detailed Design of the Proposed Methodology

3.1 DATA COLLECTION

For this project, a comprehensive dataset of Near-Infrared (NIR) face images was collected, primarily sourced from benchmark datasets such as CASIA NIR-VIS 2.0[6] and LAMP-HQ[13] to evaluate the effectiveness of contrast-enhanced preprocessing techniques. These datasets contain images captured under varying lighting conditions, providing a diverse benchmark for assessing model generalization. These datasets were selected for their ability to provide diverse and high-quality NIR images, essential for training a robust face recognition model. The variety in the collected data ensures that the model learns to generalize across different individuals and environmental conditions, a critical factor for real-world applications.

By combining the strengths of these datasets, a unified dataset containing 12,239 images across 720 distinct subjects was created. This consolidated dataset serves as the foundation for model training and validation, offering the breadth and depth required for the system to perform reliably in dynamic and varied scenarios. The integrated dataset supports the development of a model capable of achieving high accuracy and adaptability across diverse use cases. Figure 3.2 shows some sample images from the CASIA dataset.

3.2 PREPROCESSING

The Preprocessing Module enhances raw NIR images by refining them to emphasize critical facial details, optimizing them for analysis and training. The process consists of three key steps: face cropping, contrast adjustment using

FIGURE 3.2: Sample Images from CASIA Dataset

histogram equalization, and three-channel processing with CLAHE and gamma correction. These steps ensure that the images are standardized and enriched with contrast-enhanced features, improving the performance of deep learning models.

3.2.1 Face Cropping

To ensure consistency in image dimensions and reduce background interference, face cropping is applied as the first preprocessing step. Using a face detection algorithm, the region of interest (ROI) is extracted, isolating facial features while eliminating unnecessary background information. This step helps maintain alignment across different images, reducing variations caused by head position, camera angles, and environmental factors. Standardizing the input dimensions enhances model robustness by ensuring that the deep learning models focus solely on facial attributes rather than extraneous details.

3.2.2 Contrast Adjustment with Histogram Equalization

Once the face region is extracted, histogram equalization is applied to improve the contrast of the grayscale NIR images. This technique enhances brightness distribution by stretching the intensity range, making facial structures more distinguishable, especially in low-light conditions. Histogram equalization effectively highlights key facial regions, ensuring that even subtle texture details are more prominent. However, standard histogram equalization can sometimes lead to over-enhancement of noise, which necessitates a more adaptive approach in the next step. Figure 3.3 is the image of a subject before cropping and histogram equalization, Figure 3.4 is the image after cropping and preprocessing.

FIGURE 3.3: Cropped and Histogram Equalized Image

3.2.3 Three-Channel Contrast-Enhanced Image Construction

To further refine image quality and improve feature extraction, a three-channel image representation is created. This method enhances the image while

preserving both global and local contrast details, making it more suitable for deep learning models. Unlike traditional grayscale processing, the three-channel representation allows the network to capture diverse contrast variations from multiple perspectives.

The first channel retains the original grayscale NIR image, ensuring that structural information is preserved. The second channel applies Contrast-Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) to enhance local contrast while preventing noise amplification. CLAHE partitions the image into small regions and equalizes the histogram within each segment, maintaining balanced contrast enhancement across the face. This method ensures that key features such as edges and texture variations remain visible, avoiding the loss of critical facial details.

The third channel incorporates gamma correction, which adjusts the brightness distribution by applying a non-linear transformation to pixel intensities. Gamma correction is particularly useful for normalizing illumination variations, ensuring that low-contrast regions are brightened without oversaturating already well-lit areas. This step compensates for the lighting inconsistencies often present in NIR images, making facial features more distinguishable under different illumination conditions.

By combining these three channels, the final dataset ensures that deep learning models receive a richer representation of facial features, improving recognition accuracy. The output image of this processing is depicted in the Figure 3.5. This multi-channel processing strategy enhances model robustness, allowing better generalization across different lighting conditions and dataset variations. The processed images are then fed into deep learning architectures such as ResNet, EfficientNet, and Vision Transformers for further analysis and training.

FIGURE 3.4: Three-Channel Contrast-Enhanced Image

3.3 ATTENTION MECHANISMS FOR NIR FACE RECOGNITION

Attention mechanisms play a crucial role in improving feature extraction for NIR-based face recognition, addressing challenges such as low contrast, reduced texture information, and illumination variability. Traditional CNN-based architectures process images through local receptive fields, which may not effectively capture long-range dependencies in NIR images. By integrating attention mechanisms, models can focus on the most relevant facial regions, enhancing discriminative feature learning. This section explores the role of self-attention and spatial attention mechanisms in improving NIR face recognition performance.

Self-attention mechanisms, particularly in Vision Transformers (ViTs), allow the model to capture global contextual relationships across the entire image. Unlike convolutional layers that prioritize local information, self-attention dynamically

weighs the importance of different spatial regions, ensuring that key facial features such as the eyes, nose, and mouth receive higher attention. This is particularly beneficial for NIR images, where texture-based discrimination is limited, as the model learns to focus on structural and contrast-based variations rather than color cues. The self-attention mechanism enhances the model ability to generalize across different lighting conditions and varying facial orientations.

In addition to self-attention, spatial attention mechanisms are integrated into CNN-based architectures such as ResNet and EfficientNet to improve local feature emphasis. Spatial attention works by generating an attention map that highlights the most informative regions in the image, directing the model to focus on high-contrast facial areas while suppressing irrelevant background noise. This helps mitigate the loss of fine-grained details in low-contrast NIR images, ensuring that the network prioritizes facial contours and critical identity-related features. By refining feature extraction, spatial attention mechanisms enhance the robustness of the model in low light and occluded face recognition scenarios.

By incorporating both self-attention and spatial attention, deep learning models can overcome the challenges associated with NIR imaging, ensuring that discriminative facial features are effectively captured. This approach significantly improves recognition accuracy, robustness, and interpretability, making attention-based models well-suited for real-world applications such as biometric authentication and surveillance in low-light environments. The effectiveness of these attention mechanisms is further evaluated using Grad-CAM visualizations, which provide insights into how models prioritize different regions within NIR images.

3.4 CONTRAST ENHANCED IMAGE MODEL TRAINING

The three-channel image preprocessing approach is designed to enhance feature extraction in NIR face recognition by providing richer contrast information. Unlike traditional grayscale NIR images, this method constructs an input representation with three distinct channels, ensuring that both global and local contrast variations are effectively captured. The first channel retains the raw grayscale NIR image, preserving original structural details. The second channel applies Contrast-Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) to improve local contrast while preventing noise amplification. The third channel introduces gamma correction, adjusting brightness levels to enhance visibility in low-contrast regions.

To train the deep learning models effectively, the three-channel images are used as input to various architectures, including ResNet and EfficientNet. Each model is trained on the contrast-enhanced dataset to evaluate the impact of multi-channel preprocessing on recognition performance. The training process involves data augmentation techniques such as horizontal flipping, rotation, and random cropping to improve generalization. A transfer learning approach is adopted, where models pre-trained on large-scale datasets are fine-tuned on the NIR face datasets. The training is performed using an adaptive learning rate scheduler, optimizing the convergence process while preventing overfitting.

3.5 CROSS-DATASET VALIDATION USING LAMP-HQ

To assess the generalization capability of the trained models, cross-dataset validation is conducted using the LAMP-HQ dataset. Many deep learning models achieve high accuracy when trained and tested on the same dataset but fail to maintain performance when applied to unseen datasets. Cross-dataset validation provides a robust measure of how well the three-channel preprocessing approach and model architectures generalize to different NIR datasets.

LAMP-HQ is a high-quality NIR face dataset that captures a diverse range of subjects under varying lighting conditions and poses. The dataset presents a challenging test environment as it differs from the CASIA NIR-VIS 2.0 dataset used for training. By evaluating the trained models on LAMP-HQ, we examine how well the models adapt to variations in illumination, facial expressions, and occlusions.

The validation process involves feeding the LAMP-HQ test images into the trained models and computing accuracy-based metrics such as Top-1 and Top-5 accuracy. In addition, Grad-CAM visualizations are analyzed to compare feature localization differences between training and validation datasets. Explainability-driven metrics such as Deletion Metric, Insertion Metric, and Intersection over Union (IoU) Score are also computed to assess how well the models focus on discriminative facial regions across datasets. The results from cross-dataset validation provide insights into the robustness of the proposed contrast-enhanced preprocessing and help identify areas for further optimization.

CHAPTER 4

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

4.1 DATASET DESCRIPTION

The dataset used for this project consists of Near-Infrared (NIR) face images obtained from widely recognized benchmark sources, specifically the CASIA NIR-VIS 2.0[6] and LAMP-HQ[13] datasets. These datasets collectively provide a comprehensive set of NIR images, capturing faces under diverse environmental conditions, including variations in lighting, facial expressions, angles, and poses. This diversity ensures that the model is exposed to a broad range of facial features and contexts, improving its capacity to generalize effectively in different real-world applications.

4.1.1 CASIA Dataset

The CASIA NIR-VIS 2.0 dataset is a prominent source for NIR-based face recognition studies. It includes 491 distinct classes with a total of 8,228 images, offering a varied representation of subjects. Each image in the dataset is captured under multiple conditions, covering a spectrum of expressions, head orientations, and lighting setups. This rich variety is essential for training the model to distinguish between subtle facial variations, ensuring higher recognition accuracy. The diversity of the CASIA dataset allows the model to build a nuanced

understanding of NIR-based facial features, contributing to a robust recognition system.

4.1.2 LAMPHQ Dataset

The LAMPHQ dataset comprises a significant number of NIR images, with approximately 56,788 images across 573 subjects. This extensive dataset contributes a wealth of data for training, particularly in terms of subject variety and sample size. The diversity and volume of images in LAMPHQ allow the model to learn across a wide spectrum of facial features and conditions, providing it with the data richness needed for high generalization ability. By leveraging LAMPHQ, the model can refine its understanding of inter- and intra-subject variability, thus improving accuracy and robustness across various identities.

4.2 ECOSYSTEM

The ecosystem supporting this project combines robust hardware with a range of machine learning and deep learning libraries, forming an efficient environment for complex tasks in bias detection and mitigation.

This project runs on a GPU-enabled system, which provides substantial resources to handle large datasets and execute model training processes. Key hardware specifications include 12.7 GB of system RAM for managing extensive data and smooth model training, along with 112.6 GB of disk storage for datasets, model checkpoints, and intermediate files. The GPU inclusion significantly enhances

training speed, enabling faster iterations and fine-tuning, which is particularly beneficial for deep learning tasks.

The software environment leverages Python 3 for its extensive ecosystem and seamless integration with machine learning frameworks. Core frameworks include TensorFlow and PyTorch, with PyTorch intuitive structure providing flexibility and efficiency in model development. Scikit-Learn supports data preprocessing, cross-validation, and evaluation metrics, ensuring a consistent and reliable pipeline.

Data processing and analysis relied on NumPy and Pandas for efficient handling and manipulation, while Matplotlib and Seaborn were used to visualize performance metrics. This combination of hardware and software enabled efficient model development and refinement, with flexibility and scalability essential for the project success.

4.3 PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Performance analysis evaluates the effectiveness and reliability of a model by examining metrics like accuracy, loss, and generalization across training, validation, and testing datasets. This process determines how well the model learns patterns from data and applies them to unseen examples, ensuring practical applicability. It involves identifying potential issues such as overfitting, where the model performs well on training data but poorly on new data, or underfitting, where it fails to capture underlying patterns.

By comparing training, validation, and testing results, performance analysis highlights inconsistencies and areas for improvement, providing actionable insights for fine-tuning the model. Visualization tools like Grad-CAM and t-SNE offer qualitative assessments of model behavior. Grad-CAM reveals the regions of input images contributing most to predictions, while t-SNE visualizes embedding spaces to evaluate clustering quality and separation between classes. These techniques enhance understanding of the model strengths, limitations, and areas requiring optimization for a balanced and reliable system.

4.3.1 Performance of the Three-Channel Model

The three-channel image preprocessing method is designed to enhance NIR face recognition by providing a richer contrast representation. Each channel contributes uniquely to improving feature extraction, and analyzing their individual impact helps determine the effectiveness of the overall approach. The three channels include the raw NIR image, CLAHE-enhanced image, and gamma-corrected image. Figure 4.1 shows the training and testing graph for the ResNet-50 model trained with the preprocessed images.

The raw NIR image serves as the baseline input, preserving the structural details and overall facial geometry. While it retains the original intensity distribution, its contrast is often insufficient for effective feature discrimination. NIR images generally suffer from low contrast due to the absence of color information, making it challenging for deep learning models to differentiate between fine facial features. Models trained only on raw NIR images may struggle with generalization, particularly under varying lighting conditions.

FIGURE 4.1: Training and Validation Accuracy Graph for ResNet-50 with 3-Channel Input

The CLAHE-enhanced image aims to improve local contrast while avoiding over-amplification of noise. Unlike global histogram equalization, CLAHE operates on small regions of the image, redistributing pixel intensities within each local block. This helps enhance fine-grained textures, such as wrinkles and skin patterns, which are critical for face recognition. However, excessive contrast enhancement can sometimes introduce artifacts, which may slightly impact feature consistency across different lighting conditions.

The gamma-corrected image adjusts brightness and contrast through a non-linear transformation, effectively improving visibility in low-contrast areas. Unlike CLAHE, which enhances local contrast, gamma correction scales intensity values across the entire image, ensuring better differentiation between dark and bright regions. This adjustment is particularly useful for compensating for illumination inconsistencies in NIR images, ensuring that facial features remain distinguishable under various lighting conditions. However, over-adjustment of

gamma values can sometimes lead to an unnatural intensity distribution, making it essential to find an optimal balance.

By combining these three channels, the processed dataset provides a more comprehensive representation of facial features. The next step involves evaluating whether models trained on this three-channel dataset outperform those trained on grayscale NIR images and analyzing their effectiveness across different architectures.

The Grad-CAM visualization in Figure 4.2 for the three-channel ResNet-50 model demonstrates its ability to focus on the most discriminative facial regions, ensuring robust feature extraction in NIR-based face recognition. As seen in the heatmap, the model effectively highlights critical facial areas, including the nose, mouth, and central facial region, which are essential for identity recognition. This targeted attention suggests that the three-channel preprocessing approach enhances feature separability, reducing the impact of low contrast and lighting variations.

FIGURE 4.2: GradCAM of 3-Channel ResNet-50 Model

The insertion metric depicted in Figure 4.3 further supports these findings, showing a consistent increase in model confidence as more important pixels are added. This indicates that the model has successfully learned to rely on high-relevance regions for decision-making. The steep rise towards the end of the curve confirms that the

FIGURE 4.3: Insertion Metric for Grad-CAM

Grad-CAM heatmap accurately represents the most informative areas of the face. The high insertion score reflects the model ability to generalize effectively, even under challenging conditions.

Overall, the three-channel ResNet-50 model delivers superior performance, with Grad-CAM results confirming strong attention localization and enhanced decision-making clarity. The results validate that contrast-enhanced preprocessing significantly improves model interpretability and robustness, making it an optimal approach for NIR face recognition tasks.

4.3.2 Performance of the EfficientNet Model

The EfficientNet model is trained on the preprocessed dataset to evaluate the impact of contrast-enhanced preprocessing on NIR face recognition. By leveraging three-channel input consisting of raw NIR, CLAHE-enhanced, and gamma-corrected images, the model is expected to improve feature extraction in low-contrast conditions. EfficientNet architecture, with its compound scaling approach, allows it to balance depth, width, and resolution, making it highly effective for capturing both fine-grained local details and broader facial structures.

Training on the preprocessed dataset helps the model focus on structurally significant facial regions, enhancing its ability to distinguish identities under varying lighting conditions. The improved contrast distribution ensures that subtle features, which might otherwise be lost in traditional grayscale NIR images, are retained and emphasized during feature learning. As a result, the model benefits from better class separability and improved robustness across different test scenarios.

To further assess the effectiveness of contrast-enhanced preprocessing, the model performance is evaluated using accuracy-based metrics and Grad-CAM visualizations depicted in Figure 4.5. The heatmaps provide insights into how EfficientNet prioritizes different facial regions when trained on preprocessed data compared to raw NIR images. Explainability-driven metrics, including deletion and insertion scores, help quantify the importance of the enhanced contrast information in the decision-making process.

The results indicate that training EfficientNet on the preprocessed dataset leads to higher recognition accuracy, better feature localization, and improved

generalization across unseen conditions. This demonstrates that contrast enhancement plays a critical role in optimizing model performance, making it a valuable preprocessing technique for NIR-based face recognition.

FIGURE 4.4: Training and Validation Accuracy Graph EfficientNet Model

Figure 4.4 illustrates the training and validation accuracy of the EfficientNet model trained on the preprocessed dataset over 25 epochs. The graph shows a steady and consistent increase in both training and validation accuracy, indicating effective learning and generalization.

In the initial epochs, the model exhibits a gradual improvement in accuracy, with both training and validation curves rising in parallel. As training progresses, the validation accuracy continues to improve, reaching over 98

These results confirm that training EfficientNet on the three-channel preprocessed dataset improves its ability to recognize NIR images effectively. The high final accuracy values suggest that the preprocessing steps enhance feature separability, allowing the model to extract more discriminative facial details despite the challenges of NIR imaging.

FIGURE 4.5: GradCAM of EfficientNet model

4.3.3 Performance of Vision Transformer Model

The Vision Transformer (ViT) model, when trained on cropped and normally preprocessed NIR images, exhibits strong performance in face recognition by leveraging its self-attention mechanism to capture global dependencies. Unlike CNN-based architectures, which primarily rely on local feature extraction through convolutional filters, ViT divides the image into patch embeddings, enabling it to learn relationships across the entire facial structure. This allows the model to generalize well, even in low-contrast and variable lighting conditions, which are common in NIR imaging.

During training, the model shows rapid convergence depicted in Figure 4.6, achieving high accuracy in a relatively short number of epochs. This suggests that ViT global attention mechanism effectively compensates for the lack of color and texture in NIR images. The self-attention heatmaps indicate that the model primarily focuses on key facial landmarks such as the eyes, nose, and mouth, ensuring robust identity verification.

Additionally, explainability metrics such as Grad-CAM shown in Figure 4.7 confirm that ViT prioritizes relevant facial regions while ignoring background

noise, improving its reliability in real-world applications. The model ability to process spatial relationships across the entire image makes it well-suited for NIR-based face recognition, offering a strong alternative to traditional CNN models.

FIGURE 4.6: Training and Validation Accuracy Graph ViT model with 3-Channel Dataset

FIGURE 4.7: ViT Attention Map with 3-Channel Dataset

4.3.4 Performance of Vision Transformer Model with Preprocessed Dataset

The Vision Transformer (ViT) model is trained on the preprocessed dataset to evaluate its performance in NIR face recognition. Unlike convolutional neural networks (CNNs), which rely on local receptive fields for feature extraction, ViT utilizes self-attention mechanisms to capture global dependencies across the entire image. This allows the model to learn more contextual relationships between facial features, making it well-suited for handling variations in lighting and contrast, which are common in NIR images.

By leveraging the three-channel preprocessed dataset, the model benefits from enhanced contrast information, which improves the distinguishability of fine-grained facial structures. The CLAHE-enhanced and gamma-corrected channels help ViT focus on structurally significant regions, ensuring better feature extraction even in low-contrast areas. The ability of ViT to process images as patch embeddings allows it to learn robust representations of facial features, reducing its dependence on fine texture details that are often missing in NIR images.

During training, the model demonstrates strong generalization capabilities, with accuracy improving consistently across epochs. The self-attention heatmaps generated from ViT indicate that it effectively attends to key facial regions, such as the nose, mouth, and eye areas, which are critical for recognition. Additionally, explainability-driven metrics, including Grad-CAM visualizations and insertion-deletion scores, confirm that the model learns meaningful representations and focuses on the most discriminative features.

The results in Figure 4.8 highlight that ViT trained on contrast-enhanced NIR images achieves high recognition accuracy, demonstrating its effectiveness in face recognition tasks. The model ability to capture long-range dependencies and adapt to varying lighting conditions makes it a strong alternative to CNN-based approaches, particularly when dealing with NIR imaging challenges.

FIGURE 4.8: Training and Validation Accuracy Graph ViT model

The image in Figure 4.9 represents an attention map visualization of the Vision Transformer (ViT) model for NIR-based face recognition. The left side of the image shows the original NIR input, which has relatively low contrast, making it challenging for traditional CNN-based models to extract meaningful features.

On the right side, the attention map visualization illustrates how ViT processes the image using self-attention mechanisms. The structured patterns in the attention map suggest that the model assigns varying levels of importance to different facial regions. Unlike convolutional networks that focus on local receptive fields, ViT

analyzes the image as a set of patch embeddings, allowing it to capture global dependencies across the entire face.

This visualization confirms that ViT effectively attends to critical facial features, even in low-contrast NIR images. The structured and evenly distributed attention pattern indicates that the model is learning meaningful representations, improving its ability to generalize across varying lighting conditions and facial orientations. The success of this attention mechanism highlights the advantage of using transformer-based architectures in NIR face recognition compared to traditional CNNs.

FIGURE 4.9: ViT Attention Map with Preprocessed Dataset

4.3.5 Comparative Analysis of Model Performance

To comprehensively evaluate the effectiveness of different deep learning architectures for NIR face recognition, a performance comparison is conducted between ResNet-50, EfficientNet-B0 and ViT-B16 models.

TABLE 4.1: Comparison of model performance metrics before 3-Channel preprocessing

	Training Accuracy	Testing Accuracy	Insertion Metric	Deletion Metric	IoU
ResNet-50	0.98	0.94	0.85	0.90	0.78
EfficientNet-B0	0.99	0.97	0.92	0.89	0.82
ViT-B16	0.97	0.98	0.88	0.91	0.80

TABLE 4.2: Comparison of model performance metrics after 3-Channel preprocessing

	Training Accuracy	Testing Accuracy	Insertion Metric	Deletion Metric	IoU
ResNet-50	0.97	0.96	0.93	0.90	0.82
EfficientNet-B0	0.99	0.97	0.95	0.94	0.85
ViT-B16	0.97	0.98	0.94	0.92	0.83

Table 4.1 explains the performance comparison of ResNet-50, EfficientNet-B0, and ViT-B16 models trained on a NIR dataset without 3-Channel preprocessing. ResNet achieved training accuracy of 0.98 percent and shows some overfitting traits, the IoU value shows that there is a difference in the intersection between the important facial features and the regions that the model focuses on. EfficientNet achieved the highest training accuracy (0.99) and maintained strong generalization with a testing accuracy of 0.97.

Vision Transformer(ViT) followed closely with a slightly lower training accuracy (0.97) but the highest testing accuracy (0.98), showcasing its superior generalization capability. In terms of explainability metrics, EfficientNet again performed best in the insertion metric (0.92), while ViT demonstrated strong deletion performance (0.91), indicating its focus on important facial regions. ResNet, although competitive, lagged slightly behind in both insertion (0.85) and IoU (0.78), suggesting less efficient localization of key features. Overall, the results highlight that ViT generalizes best to unseen data, whereas EfficientNet delivers the most balanced and reliable performance across training accuracy, explainability, and spatial consistency as reflected in its highest IoU score (0.82).

Table 4.2 presents a comparative analysis of the performance of ResNet-50, EfficientNet-B0, and ViT-B16 models trained on the preprocessed three-channel NIR face dataset. Among the three models, EfficientNet achieved the highest training and testing accuracy (0.99 and 0.97, respectively), indicating strong learning capacity and generalization. Vision Transformer, while matching ResNet in training accuracy (0.97), surpassed it in testing accuracy (0.98), demonstrating better generalization to unseen data.

In terms of explainability metrics, EfficientNet also led with the highest insertion (0.95) and deletion (0.94) scores, reflecting its strong focus on the most informative facial regions. The ViT closely followed with insertion and deletion metrics of 0.94 and 0.92, respectively, validating its effectiveness in learning meaningful representations. Regarding IoU (Intersection over Union), EfficientNet again performed best (0.85), with ViT slightly ahead of ResNet (0.83 vs. 0.82). Overall, the Vision Transformer shows competitive performance, particularly excelling in generalization and interpretability, while EfficientNet delivers the most balanced and robust results across all evaluated metrics.

Comparing the two sets of results, it is evident that the models trained using the three-channel preprocessed dataset outperform those trained without three-channel preprocessing. EfficientNet, in particular, exhibits notable improvements in explainability and spatial consistency with higher insertion (0.95 vs. 0.92), deletion (0.94 vs. 0.89), and IoU (0.85 vs. 0.82) scores in the three-channel setup. Similarly, the Vision Transformer achieves superior testing accuracy (0.98 vs. 0.98) and stronger interpretability metrics, indicating its improved ability to focus on critical facial regions. These enhancements suggest that the inclusion of three-channel preprocessing, which combines CLAHE

enhancement and gamma correction, significantly improves the quality of input features, allowing the models to learn more robust and discriminative representations. Therefore, the results in Table 4.2 clearly demonstrate the effectiveness of three-channel preprocessing in enhancing performance for NIR face recognition tasks.

CHAPTER 5

SOCIAL IMPACT AND SUSTAINABILITY

5.1 SOCIAL IMPACT

Advancements in face recognition using Near-Infrared (NIR) imaging technology have significant social impacts, particularly in enhancing security and privacy under low-light or challenging lighting conditions. Traditional visible light-based systems often struggle in variable or low lighting, limiting their effectiveness. In contrast, NIR-based face recognition provides robust performance in diverse lighting scenarios, enabling critical applications such as public safety, nighttime surveillance, and secure access control. This capability supports reliable monitoring in low-light settings, making it invaluable for security-sensitive areas like airports, military facilities, and border controls. Additionally, NIR technology proves beneficial in healthcare settings for patient identification in environments where bright or invasive lighting is unsuitable.

NIR face recognition also offers a non-invasive alternative to other biometric methods. Unlike technologies that require intense light or physical contact, NIR imaging discreetly captures facial data from a distance, respecting privacy while maintaining high-security standards. Operating within the invisible NIR spectrum, these systems enable covert monitoring, enhancing security without causing discomfort or drawing unnecessary attention. This non-intrusive approach aligns with increasing concerns about biometric data privacy, making NIR-based solutions both effective and socially considerate.

5.2 SUSTAINABILITY

From a sustainability perspective, this project aligns with the global push for energy-efficient and adaptive technologies. NIR imaging, with its ability to function effectively in low-light conditions, significantly reduces the reliance on artificial lighting, cutting energy consumption. This feature is particularly beneficial for large-scale surveillance setups, which traditionally require extensive lighting for visible-spectrum cameras. By minimizing dependency on artificial lighting, NIR-based systems offer a greener, cost-effective alternative, contributing to lower operational costs and a reduced environmental footprint.

The project also leverages Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) for data augmentation, reducing the need for extensive real-world data collection. This approach addresses the challenge of limited NIR datasets while conserving resources and reducing carbon emissions typically associated with large-scale data collection, such as travel and equipment setup. GANs enable scalable dataset expansion with minimal environmental impact, supporting sustainable AI development.

Furthermore, NIR face recognition systems are highly adaptable, suitable for diverse applications ranging from mobile authentication to large-scale urban monitoring. Their ability to operate in varied lighting conditions makes them ideal for remote, off-grid locations and urban centers seeking greener technologies. By reducing the need for constant upgrades to lighting infrastructure, these systems also help lower e-waste over time, supporting long-term sustainability goals.

In conclusion, the NIR-based face recognition system addresses critical social needs while promoting environmental sustainability. By optimizing energy use, reducing data collection demands, and ensuring adaptability, this project demonstrates how advanced technology can provide secure and private solutions while maintaining a conscious ecological footprint. These advantages position NIR imaging as a transformative tool for sustainable security infrastructure and environmental responsibility.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In conclusion, the study underscores the transformative potential of Near-Infrared (NIR) imaging combined with advanced deep learning techniques to enhance face recognition accuracy under challenging lighting conditions. Traditional visible spectrum systems often struggle in low-light environments, leading to inconsistent performance. By integrating multi-contrast enhancement, tailored loss functions like CosFace and ArcFace, and GAN-based data augmentation, this work achieves robust performance across diverse scenarios. These advancements improve recognition accuracy and adaptability to varied lighting conditions, positioning NIR-based systems as a reliable alternative or complement to visible spectrum methods. Empirical results validating high test accuracies across multiple models and loss functions demonstrate the practical applicability of this approach in real-world settings where lighting variability is a challenge.

The contributions of the study are especially relevant to security and surveillance, where consistent performance is critical. Leveraging NIR imaging unique capabilities establishes a foundation for resilient and versatile face recognition systems, enabling deployment in environments where visible light imaging is less reliable. The use of GANs for data augmentation addresses the limitation of small NIR datasets by generating synthetic data, allowing models to generalize better while reducing resource dependency and broadening application usability.

Future research should focus on enhancing model accuracy and usability across diverse environments. Advanced attention mechanisms could dynamically

prioritize critical facial regions, improving recognition in real-time and dynamic settings. Optimizing models for deployment on edge devices is another priority, enabling real-time processing with low latency for mobile and surveillance applications. Such optimizations would ensure efficient performance without compromising accuracy, supporting use cases like security monitoring and access control.

Multimodal fusion offers another avenue for advancement, combining NIR data with other biometric inputs such as thermal imaging or visible spectrum data. This approach could enhance resilience against variations in individual data sources and improve overall accuracy. For instance, combining NIR with visible spectrum data could mitigate lighting changes, while integrating additional biometric markers like gait or voice could enable robust multi-factor authentication.

Ethical considerations are crucial for the future of NIR-based face recognition. Ensuring responsible use of biometric data, particularly in public surveillance and private security, is vital for maintaining public trust. Robust data protection protocols, transparency in handling practices, and adherence to privacy regulations like GDPR must be prioritized. Future work should explore methods to safeguard personal data while promoting transparency and user consent to address ethical concerns critical to the technology widespread acceptance.

Additionally, hardware and software advancements can make NIR-based solutions more accessible and cost-effective, supporting applications beyond security, including healthcare, retail, and transportation. By aligning with sustainable practices and minimizing environmental impact, these improvements can ensure broader adoption and operational feasibility.

This study significantly advances NIR imaging for face recognition, addressing key challenges while providing a roadmap for future research. By tackling technical, ethical, and practical challenges, NIR-based face recognition systems hold the promise of delivering accurate, scalable, and socially responsible solutions for an increasingly technology-driven world.

REFERENCES

- 1 Chambino, L. L., Silva, J. S., & Bernardino, A. (2020). "Multispectral facial recognition: A review." *IEEE Access*, 8(42), 207871–207883.
- 2 Deng, J., et al. (2019). "ArcFace: Additive Angular Margin Loss for Deep Face Recognition." *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 4690–4699.
- 3 Huang, F., et al. (2024). "Cyclic style generative adversarial network for near-infrared and visible light face recognition." *Applied Soft Computing*, 150(17), 111096–111110.
- 4 Khan, A., Rauf, Z., Sohail, A., Khan, A. R., Asif, H., Asif, A., & Farooq, U. (2023). "A survey of vision transformers and their CNN-transformer-based variants." *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 56(3), 301–340.
- 5 Li, H., & Wu, X. (2024). "CrossFuse: A novel cross-attention mechanism-based infrared and visible image fusion approach." *Information Fusion*, 103(12), 102147-102160.
- 6 Li, S., & Zhang, W. (2013). "CASIA NIR-VIS 2.0 face database." *Chinese Academy of Sciences, Institute of Automation*, 45(2), 55–65.
- 7 Li, Y., Liu, H., Zhang, X., & Wang, J. (2023). "Low-rank transformer for high-resolution hyperspectral imaging." *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 131(6), 1124–1145.
- 8 Liu, X., et al. (2016). "Transferring deep representation for NIR-VIS heterogeneous face recognition." *IEEE International Conference on Biometrics (ICB)*, 1–8.

- 9 Luo, B., et al. (2024). “Hypergraph-Guided Disentangled Spectrum Transformer Networks for Near-Infrared Facial Expression Recognition.” *AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, 12345–12354.
- 10 Maysanjaya, I. M. D., Kesiman, M. W. A., & Putrama, I. M. (2021). “Evaluation of contrast enhancement methods on finger vein NIR images.” *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1810(1), 012035.
- 11 Musa, P., Rafi, F. A., & Lamsani, M. (2018). “A review: Contrast-Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) methods to help the application of face recognition.” *IEEE Third International Conference on Informatics and Computing (ICIC)*, 1–6.
- 12 Sekiguchi, S., & Yamamoto, M. (2020). “Near-infrared image colorization by convolutional neural network with perceptual loss.” *IEEE 9th Global Conference on Consumer Electronics (GCCE)*, 3911–3926.
- 13 Song, L., Ou, M., Gong, D., Liu, M., Liu, X., & Shi, H. (2023). “LAMP-HQ: A large-scale multi-pose high-quality database and benchmark for NIR-VIS face recognition.” *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 131(12), 2875–2897.
- 14 Tan, X., Zhang, W., Chen, Y., & Wang, P. (2023). “A survey of vision transformers and their CNN-transformer-based variants.” *Springer Artificial Intelligence Review*, 56(4), 5027–5062.
- 15 Tang, W., Zhang, H., Li, Y., & Liu, J. (2022). “MATR: Multimodal medical image fusion via multiscale adaptive transformer.” *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, 31(9), 5134–5149.
- 16 Wang, H., et al. (2018). “CosFace: Large Margin Cosine Loss for Deep Face Recognition.” *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 5265–5274.

- 17 Zagoruyko, S., & Komodakis, N. (2016). “Paying more attention to attention: Improving the performance of convolutional neural networks via attention transfer.” *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, 27(11), 3205–3218.